

Thermodynamic Study of the Complexation Reaction of Some Solochrome Dyes with Lanthanum, Cerium, Thorium and Uranium

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The thermodynamic parameters for the complexation of four solochrome dyes viz., Solo yellow 2 GS, Solo Black W DFA, Solo 6 BN and Solo Fast Navy 2 RS, with lanthanum, cerium, thorium and uranium have been determined potentiometrically, at 28° and 44° and at an ionic strength of $\mu=0.1$, in aqueous solutions. The step wise values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have also been evaluated.

A vast variety of metal-dye complexes are employed commercially, amongst which, azo dyes are the ones most extensively used¹. Two types of azo dyes are most important: (i) the azo salicylic acid and (ii) O-O'-dihydroxy azo dyes. In the present communication, we report the results of our investigations on the thermo-dynamic parameters of complexation of four such azo dyes (also called solochrome dyes) with lanthanum, cerium, thorium and uranium. The names and structures of the dyes are given below:

Experimental

Standard carbonate free potassium hydroxide² was used for potentiometric titrations. HClO₄ (Anala R, BDH) was used in all titrations. Solutions of lanthanum(III) chloride, cerium(IV) nitrate, thorium(IV) nitrate and uranyl(VI) acetate [UO₂(CH₃COO)₂ · 2H₂O] (all BDH materials) were prepared in water distilled from alkaline potassium permanganate solution and then redistilled twice and their strengths determined as usual.^{2,3}

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The solochrome dyes were obtained from ICI, India. They were purified by recrystallisation from 50% ethanol, dried over silica gel and tested for their purity by chromatography.⁴ Solutions of the dyes were prepared in double distilled water from weighed amount and allowed to stand overnight before use. The solution of Solo 6 BN was prepared in 5% ethanol.

pH measurements were carried out on a battery-operated bench type cambridge pH meter, using glass and calomel electrodes. The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffers. The titrations were carried out in a thermostated water bath at 20° ± 0.1° and 44° ± 0.1°.

Procedure:

The following solutions (total volume 20 ml) were titrated pH meterically against 0.1 M KOH.

- (i) 5.0 ml of 0.0392 M HClO₄
- (ii) 5.0 ml of 0.0392 M HClO₄ + 5.0 ml of 0.01 to 0.005 M dye.
- (iii) 5.0 ml of 0.00392 M HClO₄ + 5.0 ml of 0.01 to 0.005 M dye + 5.0 ml of .002 M Metal.

A constant ionic strength of 0.1 was maintained in each titration by adding the requisite amount of KCl₄O.

The protonation and formation constants were determined by the Calvin Bjerrum method^{5,6} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷.

Results and Discussion

The "practical" proton-ligand stability constants for the dyes were calculated⁷ by plotting $\log K_A$

versus pH and are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE-1 PROTON LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SOLOCHROME DYES

Dye	T°C	Log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H	log B _n ^H
Solochrome	20	9.85	-	9.85
Yellow 2GS	44	9.20	-	9.20
Solochrome	20	11.50	7.00	18.50
Black W DFA	44	10.90	6.50	17.40
Solochrome	20	11.10	7.15	18.25
6 BN	44	10.95	6.80	17.75
Solochrome	20	11.80	9.20	21.00
Fast Navy 2RS	44	10.80	9.50	20.30

The step wise stability constant of a complex is given by,

$$K_n = \frac{C_{ML_n}}{C_{ML_{n-1}} \cdot C_L} \quad (\text{where } n=1, 2, \dots, N)$$

Where K_n represents the nth metal-ligand stability constant. The stepwise stability constant was obtained by us from a plot of $\bar{n}$ against pL. The value of $\bar{n}$, the average number of ligands attached per metal ion is given by,

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V^{III} - V^{II}) (N^{\circ} + E^{\circ})}{(V^{\circ} + V^{\ddagger}) \bar{n}_A T_{CM}^{\circ}}$$

While the free ligand exponent, pL is given by,

$$pL = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n=j} \beta_n^H (1/\text{anti log pH})^n (V^{\circ} + V^{III})}{(T_{CL}^{\circ} - \bar{n} T_{CM}^{\circ}) V^{\circ}} \right]$$

TABLE-2 Formation Constants of Metal Complexes of Solochrome Dyes

Dye	T°	La(III)			Ce(IV)			Th(IV)			U(VI)		
		Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log β ₂	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log β ₂	Log K ₁	Log β ₂	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log β ₂	
Solo Y-2GS	20	8.7	-	8.7	9.3	8.4	17.7	9.4	7.2	16.6	8.2	-	8.2
	44	8.5	-	8.5	8.9	8.0	16.9	8.8	7.3	16.1	8.1	-	8.1
Solo B-W DFA	20	10.6	-	10.6	13.4	5.9	19.3	14.6	11.1	25.7	8.8	-	8.8
	44	10.6	-	10.2	13.7	6.3	20.0	14.5	12.2	26.7	8.9	-	8.9
Solo 6BN	20	10.7	-	10.7	13.9	8.2	22.1	14.7	8.9	23.6	9.7	-	9.7
	44	11.9	-	11.9	14.3	8.3	22.6	15.0	9.7	24.7	10.6	-	10.6
Solo F. Navy 2RS	20	12.4	-	12.4	16.1	11.4	27.5	18.0	13.3	31.3	11.2	-	11.2
	44	12.5	-	12.5	17.3	10.6	27.9	19.7	12.5	32.2	11.4	-	11.4

TABLE-3 Free Energy of Metal-Dye Complexes (k cal mol⁻¹)

Dye	T°	La(III)			Ce(IV)			Th(IV)			U(VI)		
		-ΔG ₁	-ΔG ₂	-ΔG									
Solo Y-2GS	20	11.62	-	11.62	12.42	11.22	23.64	12.55	9.61	22.16	10.95	-	10.95
	44	12.28	-	12.28	12.86	11.56	24.42	12.72	10.55	23.27	11.70	-	11.70
Solo B-W DFA	20	14.16	-	14.16	17.90	9.97	27.87	19.50	14.83	34.33	11.75	-	11.75
	44	14.74	-	14.74	19.87	9.10	28.97	20.95	17.63	38.58	12.86	-	12.86
Solo 6 BN	20	14.29	-	14.29	18.57	10.95	29.52	19.64	11.89	31.53	12.95	-	12.95
	44	17.20	-	17.20	20.67	11.99	32.66	21.68	14.02	35.70	15.32	-	15.32
Solo F. Navy 2RS	20	16.56	-	16.56	21.51	15.23	36.74	24.04	17.76	41.80	14.96	-	14.96
	44	18.06	-	18.06	25.00	15.32	40.32	28.47	18.06	46.53	16.47	-	16.47

TABLE-4 Enthalpy of Metal-Dyes Complexes (in k cal mol⁻¹)

Dye	ΔH ₁	La(III)			Ce(IV)			Th(IV)			U(VI)		
		ΔH ₁	ΔH ₂	ΔH	ΔH ₁	ΔH ₂	ΔH	ΔH ₁	ΔH ₂	ΔH	ΔH ₁	ΔH ₂	ΔH
Solo Y-2GS	-3.52	-	-3.52	-7.05	-7.05	-14.10	-10.58	1.76	-8.82	-1.76	-	-1.76	
Solo B-W DFA	-7.05	-	-7.05	6.17	7.05	13.22	-1.76	19.41	17.64	1.76	-	1.76	
Solo 6 BN	21.17	-	21.17	7.05	1.76	8.81	-5.29	14.11	19.40	15.88	-	15.88	
Solo F. Navy 2RS	1.76	-	1.76	21.17	-14.11	7.06	30.00	-14.11	15.89	3.52	-	3.52	

TABLE-5 Entropy Data on Metal-Dye Complexes (in Cal dgree⁻¹ mol⁻¹)

DYE	T°	La(III)			Ce(IV)			Th(IV)			U(VI)		
		ΔS ₁	ΔS ₂	ΔS	ΔS ₁	ΔS ₂	ΔS	ΔS ₁	ΔS ₂	ΔS	ΔS ₁	ΔS ₂	ΔS
Solo Y-2GS	20	27.62	-	27.62	18.31	14.21	32.52	6.60	26.80	33.40	31.36	-	31.36
	44	27.62	-	27.62	18.31	14.21	32.52	6.72	27.77	34.49	31.36	-	31.26
Solo B-W DFA	20	24.24	-	24.24	81.41	58.12	139.53	61.01	106.82	167.83	46.14	-	46.14
	44	22.41	-	22.41	82.17	50.99	133.26	62.83	73.91	136.74	46.46	-	46.46
Solo-6BN	20	121.06	-	121.06	67.75	43.43	111.15	85.09	82.04	167.13	98.43	-	98.43
	44	66.80	-	66.80	87.47	43.40	130.88	85.09	88.76	173.85	98.43	-	98.43
Solo F. Navy	20	62.56	-	62.56	145.68	3.80	149.48	184.46	12.46	196.92	62.77	-	62.77
	44	62.56	-	62.56	145.68	3.83	149.48	184.46	12.46	196.92	63.11	-	63.11

The formation curves for lanthanum, cerium, Thorium and uranium with solo-chrome dyes are given in Figs. 1-4.

The estimated uncertainties in the thermodynamic parameters are ± 0.5 K Cal/mol in ΔH and ± 2 e u in ΔS .

FIG.1 - Formation curves of Solo.F. Navy 2RS complexes .

Fig. 4 Formation curves of Solo. Y-1GS complexes.

FIG.2 - Formation curves of Solo.B- W DFA complexes .

FIG.3 - Formation curves of Solo. 6BN complexes .

The values of $\bar{n}$ were less than 1.5 for the complexes of lanthanum and uranium and did not exceed 2.0 in the case of cerium and thorium, thereby showing the formation of only 1 : 1 complexes in the former cases and both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in the latter cases. The values of the concentration, stability constants at an ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$ (Table 2), were used to calculate the thermodynamic parameters (Tables 3-5) from the following relations :

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K$$

$$\ln K_2, K_1 = \frac{\Delta H}{R} \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 \cdot T_2}$$

and $\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$

An examination of the stability constants (Table 2) shows that Solochrome yellow 2GS forms the least stable complexes while Solochrome fast Navy 2RS forms the most stable complexes. Further the values of $\log \beta_n$ for Solo 6BN and Solo B. W DFA show that introduction of an NO_2 group (Electron withdrawing) lowers the stability of the resulting complex. Also the dyes with two OH groups (O-O dihydroxy) form more stable complexes than the dyes with one OH group (Solo. Y-2GS) due to the formation of more stable ring across the azo bridging.

The stability of the complexes follows the order :
Solo. Y-2GS < Solo. B-WDFA < Solo. 6 BN <
Solo F. Navy 2RS

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